

Survey of Disease Detection with Machine Learning Algorithms

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Abstract: In the field of medical imaging, Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD) has emerged as a rapidly evolving area of research. The recent focus has been on improving CAD applications due to the critical impact that inaccuracies in medical diagnostic systems can have on patient treatment. A key component in enhancing CAD is machine learning. Traditional methods may not always accurately represent complex structures like organs, highlighting the need for advanced pattern recognition which is inherent in machine learning. In biomedical applications, the integration of pattern recognition and machine learning is seen as a pathway to enhance the precision and objectivity in diagnosing various diseases. These technologies are particularly adept at processing and interpreting high-dimensional and multimodal biomedical data, leading to the development of sophisticated, automated algorithms. This paper conducts a comparative analysis of diverse machine learning algorithms applied to the diagnosis of several diseases, including heart disease, diabetes, liver disease, dengue, and hepatitis. It aims to showcase the array of machine learning tools and techniques employed in disease analysis and the subsequent decision-making processes, providing valuable insights into the efficacy of these algorithms in medical diagnostics.

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Introduction

Machine Learning (ML), a key component of Artificial Intelligence (AI), operates by learning from data through various algorithms, continually enhancing its performance by making adjustments throughout the learning process. ML's applications span numerous fields, including robotics, education, travel, and notably, healthcare. In the healthcare

sector, ML is primarily utilized for disease diagnosis. The journey of ML in healthcare began in the 1970s, and by 1980, the field had gained enough prominence to warrant the establishment of an international journal, *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*. Over the following two decades, the domain of disease diagnosis incorporated classical ML techniques such as Support Vector Machine, Naïve Bayes, and early forms of artificial neural networks. A significant milestone in this evolution was the introduction of AlexNet in 2012, marking the onset of the deep learning era in healthcare, where neural networks showed exceptional capabilities. The past decade has witnessed a substantial surge in investment in AI and healthcare applications. Various studies highlight the emergence of AI and ML technologies in healthcare, leading to the creation of innovative software, platforms, automated systems, and devices aimed at monitoring and enhancing patient health.

Analyzing clinical data through Machine Learning (ML) can significantly expedite disease diagnosis, enabling earlier treatment for patients. Traditional methods of diagnosing diseases are often expensive and time-consuming. However, the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of ML-based approaches for disease diagnosis have been well-documented by researchers. These ML techniques are adept at diagnosing both common and rare diseases. Recent studies have highlighted the effectiveness and robustness of AI and ML in addressing healthcare challenges, underscoring their potential in transforming disease diagnosis and patient care.

Generally, when developing an ML model for disease diagnosis, the dataset is structured as a table with various attribute columns and a specific column for the class variable. This class variable is crucial as it indicates the diagnosis status of each instance in the dataset. A common coding convention is to use '1' to signify a positive diagnosis and '0' for a negative diagnosis. The analysis of healthcare data frequently employs both supervised and unsupervised ML techniques. However, disease diagnosis tasks predominantly rely on supervised learning. A thorough examination of the dataset and the ML algorithms employed will be provided in Section 2 of our study.

In this research, we focused on a healthcare dataset concerning diabetes. Specifically, we utilized the widely recognized Pima Indian Diabetes Dataset, a common benchmark for assessing machine learning algorithms [17,18]. This dataset was acquired from [18]. It comprises eight features and a target variable labeled 'Outcome', which indicates diabetes diagnosis with values 0 (negative) or 1 (positive). The dataset contains 768 records, including 268 individuals diagnosed with diabetes.

2.1.1. Data Exploration

Within this dataset, two features, namely Body Mass Index (BMI) and Diabetes Pedigree Function, are continuous numerical values, while the others are discrete numerical integers. Notably, all features are complete without any missing data. Table 1 provides an extensive statistical analysis of each feature.

Table 1. Statistical description of data based on attributes.

Figure 1. Types of machine learning techniques.

Supervised, unsupervised, and semi-supervised learning are key methodologies used in machine learning to categorize and analyze data sets.

1. Supervised Learning: This method involves training algorithms with a pre-defined set of examples and their corresponding outcomes. The algorithm is then able to make accurate predictions or decisions for new inputs. This type of learning is akin to learning through examples. It can be further divided into:

Classification: This approach is used for making binary (Yes/No) predictions, such as determining if a tumor is cancerous or if a product meets quality standards.

Regression: Used for predicting quantities or values, answering questions like "How much?" or "How many?".

2. Unsupervised Learning: Unlike supervised learning, unsupervised learning does not use labeled outcomes for training. Instead, it focuses on identifying patterns and similarities within the input data to categorize it. This method is also referred to as finding hidden structures in data. A common application is:

- Clustering: Creating groups or clusters based on the similarities found in the data.

3. Semi-Supervised Learning: This approach is a hybrid of the previous two. It utilizes a small set of labeled data along with a larger set of unlabeled data for training. Semi-supervised learning is beneficial when acquiring labeled data is expensive or time-consuming, providing a middle ground between supervised (relying on labeled data) and unsupervised learning (relying on unlabeled data).

Machine learning encompasses various methodologies, each with unique characteristics and applications:

4. Reinforcement Learning: This technique is inspired by behaviorist psychology. It involves training algorithms through a trial-and-error process, where the algorithm learns from the consequences of its actions rather than from explicit instruction. The algorithm receives feedback when an action is incorrect but must discover the correct action on its own. This method is sometimes referred to as learning with a critic, as it does not provide specific guidance for improvement. Reinforcement learning is distinct from supervised learning as it does not rely on a predefined set of correct input/output pairs.

5. Evolutionary Learning: Drawing parallels with biological evolution, this method applies the concept of survival of the fittest to machine learning. It adapts and evolves algorithms based on their effectiveness, similar to how organisms evolve to improve survival and reproductive success. This approach uses the concept of 'fitness' to evaluate solutions, applying this biological model to computational problems.

6. Deep Learning: A subset of machine learning, deep learning uses complex architectures composed of multiple layers to model high-level abstractions in data. These architectures, known as deep neural networks, involve a series of linear

and non-linear transformations. Deep learning has been instrumental in advancements in areas like pattern recognition and data classification, significantly impacting fields like healthcare.

In healthcare, machine learning plays a crucial role in diagnostic processes, assisting in the interpretation and management of vast amounts of medical data. These technologies help organize and process data for effective diagnosis and treatment, enhancing the capabilities of decision support systems. Machine learning algorithms, particularly in modern hospitals, facilitate the collection, analysis, and sharing of medical data, leading to more accurate and efficient patient care. These systems not only aid experienced physicians in diagnostics but also provide valuable tools for training medical students and non-specialists.

In past, ML has offered self-driving cars, speech detection, efficient web search, and improved perception of the human generation. Today machine learning is present everywhere so that without knowing it, one can possibly use it many times a day. A lot of researchers consider it as the excellent way in moving towards human level. The machine learning techniques discovers electronic health record that generally contains high dimensional patterns and multiple data sets. Pattern recognition is the theme of MLT that offers support to predict and make decisions for diagnosis and to plan treatment. Machine learning algorithms are capable to manage huge number of data, to combine data from dissimilar resources, and to integrate the background information in the study [3]

2. Diagnosis of Diseases by Using Different Machine Learning Algorithms

Numerous studies have been conducted on the application of machine learning algorithms for disease diagnosis, with researchers widely acknowledging the effectiveness of these methods in identifying various health conditions. A typical representation of diseases diagnosed using machine learning techniques might include conditions such as heart disease, diabetes, liver disorders, dengue fever, and hepatitis. These diseases, each with their unique diagnostic challenges and patterns, can be effectively identified and analyzed through specialized machine learning algorithms, demonstrating the versatility and efficacy of these techniques in the medical field.

2.1. Heart Disease

Otoom and colleagues conducted a study where they developed a system for analyzing and monitoring coronary artery disease. They utilized the Cleveland heart dataset from the UCI repository, which comprises 303 individual cases with 76 distinct attributes or features. For their analysis, they selectively used 13 out of these 76 features. The study involved conducting two tests using three different machine learning algorithms: Bayes Net, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Functional Trees (FT). These tests aimed at detecting coronary artery disease. For the implementation and testing of these algorithms, the researchers employed the WEKA software tool, a popular platform for data mining and machine learning applications. The study's focus was on assessing the effectiveness of these algorithms in accurately detecting coronary artery disease using a subset of features from a comprehensive dataset.

Figure 2. Diseases diagnosed by MLT.

Several studies have focused on using machine learning algorithms for diagnosing heart disease and other conditions, each employing different techniques and datasets to evaluate their effectiveness.

- Otoom et al.'s study involved using the Cleveland heart dataset from UCI, focusing on 13 out of 76 features. They used Bayes Net, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Functional Trees (FT) algorithms. In their holdout test, the SVM achieved an 88.3% accuracy rate. Cross-validation tests showed that both SVM and Bayes Net attained an accuracy of 83.8%, and FT achieved 81.5%. By selecting the 7 best features through a Best First selection algorithm, Bayes Net reached 84.5% accuracy, SVM 85.1%, and FT 84.5%.
- Vembandasamy et al. conducted a study to diagnose heart disease using the Naive Bayes algorithm. The data, from a diabetic research institute in Chennai, included information on 500 patients. Using Weka for classification with a 70% percentage split, the Naive Bayes algorithm showed an accuracy of 86.419%.
- Chaurasia and Pal suggested using data mining approaches for heart disease detection. Employing the WEKA tool and a dataset from UCI with 76 attributes (of which only 11 were used), they tested Naive Bayes, J48, and bagging algorithms. Naive Bayes achieved 82.31% accuracy, J48 84.35%, and Bagging 85.03%, with Bagging providing the best classification rate.
- Parthiban and Srivatsa focused on diagnosing heart disease in diabetic patients using Naive Bayes and SVM algorithms in WEKA. They used a dataset of 500 patients from a Chennai research institute, with 142 diagnosed and 358 without the disease. Naive Bayes showed 74% accuracy, while SVM yielded a higher accuracy of 94.60%.
- Tan et al. proposed a hybrid technique combining Genetic Algorithm (GA) and SVM, using the wrapper approach. Their study utilized LIBSVM and WEKA tools, examining five datasets from the UC Irvine machine learning repository (Iris, Diabetes, Breast Cancer, Heart, and Hepatitis). For heart disease, the GA and SVM hybrid approach achieved an 84.07% accuracy rate, with varying accuracies for other diseases, such as 78.26% for diabetes and 86.12% for hepatitis. Each study highlights the diverse applications and effectiveness of machine learning algorithms in diagnosing various diseases, showcasing the potential of these technologies in healthcare.

Figure 3. Machine learning algorithm's accuracy to detect heart disease.

Table 1. Comprehensive view of machine learning techniques for heart disease diagnosis.

Machine Learning Techniques	Author	Year	Disease	Resources of Data Set	Tool	Accuracy
Bayes Net						84.5%
SVM	Otoom <i>et al.</i>	2015	CAD (Coronary artery disease)	UCI	WEKA	85.1%
FT						84.5%
Naive Bayes	Vembandasamy <i>et al.</i>	2015	Heart Disease	Diabetic Research Institute in Chennai	WEKA	86.419%
Naive Bayes						82.31%
J48	Chaurasia and Pal	2013	Heart Disease	UCI	WEKA	84.35%
Bagging						85.03%
SVM	Parthiban and Srivatsa	2012	Heart disease	Research institute in Chennai	WEKA	94.60%
Naive Bayes						74%
Hybrid Technique (GA + SVM)	Tan <i>et al.</i>	2009	Heart disease	UCI	LIBSVM and WEKA	84.07%

Advantages and Disadvantages of SVM:

Advantages: Construct correct classifiers and fewer over fitting, robust to noise. Disadvantages: It is a binary classifier. For the classification of multi-class, it can use pair wise classification. Its Computational cost is high, so it runs slow [10].

2.2. Diabetes Disease

In their study on predicting diabetes, Iyer et al. focused on using decision tree and Naive Bayes algorithms. They addressed diabetes, a condition characterized by insufficient insulin production or improper insulin utilization. The research utilized the Pima Indian diabetes dataset and conducted various tests using the WEKA data mining tool.

In their analysis, they found that the percentage split method (70:30 ratio) yielded better results than cross-validation for this particular dataset. Specifically, the J48 algorithm showed an accuracy of 74.8698% with cross-validation and an improved accuracy of 76.9565% using the percentage split method. The Naive Bayes algorithm demonstrated even higher accuracy, reaching 79.5652% when using the percentage split test. These findings indicate that the choice of testing method (cross-validation vs. percentage split) can significantly impact the accuracy of the algorithms in predicting diabetes. The study underscores the importance of selecting appropriate methodologies for data analysis in medical research, especially in the context of disease prediction and diagnosis. Several researchers have explored

machine learning algorithms for the diagnosis of diabetes, using various methods and datasets to evaluate their effectiveness.

They employed the Pima Indians diabetes dataset from the UCI Machine Learning Laboratory and used WEKA for analysis. Their study tested algorithms like CART, Adaboost, Logitboost, and Grading for diabetes diagnosis. The results indicated that CART had the highest accuracy at 78.646%, followed by Adaboost with 77.864%, Logitboost at 77.479%, and Grading at 66.406%. These findings were based on the rates of correct and incorrect classifications.

Their experiment focused on using the SVM technique, specifically with the RBF kernel, for classifying diabetes. They also used the Pima Indian diabetes dataset from the University of California, Irvine, and conducted the experiment with MATLAB 2010a, achieving an accuracy of 78%. They proposed using the Naive Bayes algorithm to predict Type-2 diabetes. Their dataset consisted of 415 cases from various sections of Indian society. The model development utilized MATLAB in conjunction with SQL server, achieving a high prediction accuracy of 95%.

This study developed a model combining Genetic Algorithm (GA) and fuzzy logic for diabetes diagnosis. The model aimed to select the best subset of features to enhance classification accuracy. Using a dataset from the UCI Machine Learning Laboratory with 8 attributes and 769 cases, the experiment was conducted in MATLAB. The GA selected three key features for the fuzzy logic classifier, which then achieved an accuracy of 87%.

In summary, these studies demonstrate the potential of various machine learning techniques in diagnosing diabetes. Naive Bayes, in particular, has shown high accuracy rates, though its effectiveness varied across studies. The evolving nature of these algorithms and their application in medical diagnosis highlights the importance of continuous research and development in this field.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Naive Bayes:

Advantages: It enhances the classification performance by eliminating the un-related features. Its performance is good. It takes less computational time.

Figure 4. Accuracy of machine learning algorithms to detect diabetes disease.

Disadvantages: This algorithm needs large amount of data to attain good out-comes. It is lazy as they store entire the training examples [16].

2.3. Liver Disease

Several studies have explored the use of machine learning algorithms for the diagnosis of liver disease, each employing different techniques and datasets:

Vijayarani and Dhayanand conducted a study using the ILPD dataset from UCI, applying Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Naive Bayes classification algorithms. Their comparison focused on accuracy and execution time. The results showed Naive Bayes achieving 61.28% accuracy in 1670.00 ms, while SVM attained a higher accuracy of 79.66% but took longer at 3210.00 ms. MATLAB was used for implementation, with SVM outperforming Naive Bayes in terms of accuracy for liver disease prediction, though Naive Bayes was faster.

Gulia et al analyzed liver patient data using the WEKA data mining tool and five intelligent techniques: J48, MLP, Random Forest, SVM, and Bayesian Network classifiers. The study was conducted in three steps: applying algorithms to the original dataset, using feature selection methods to identify significant subsets, and comparing results before and after feature selection. Post-feature selection, J48 achieved 70.669% accuracy, MLP 70.8405%, SVM 71.3551%, Random Forest 71.8696%, and Bayesian Network 69.1252%.

Rajeswari and Reena** focused on liver disease analysis using data mining algorithms Naive Bayes, K star, and FT tree. Their dataset, also from UCI, included 345 instances with 7 attributes. Using 10-fold cross-validation in WEKA, they found Naive Bayes to have 96.52% accuracy, FT tree 97.10%, and K star 83.47%. The FT tree showed the highest classification accuracy for the liver disease dataset among the tested algorithms.

These studies highlight the diverse applications and efficacy of different machine learning algorithms in the diagnosis of liver disease, showcasing the potential of these technologies in medical diagnostics.

Analysis:

To diagnose liver disease, FT Tree Algorithm provides the highest result as compared to the other algorithms. When FT tree algorithm is applied on the dataset of liver disease, time taken for result or building the model is fast as compared to other algorithms. According to its attribute, it shows the improved performance. This algorithm fully classified the attributes and offers 97.10% correctness. From the results, this Algorithm plays an important role in determining enhanced classification accuracy of data set. Accuracy graph of algorithms are shown in Figure 5.

Advantages and Disadvantages of FT:

Advantage: Easy to interpret and understand; Fast prediction.

Disadvantage: Calculations are complex mainly if values are uncertain or if several outcomes are linked.

2.4. Dengue Disease

Tarmizi et al. [20] performed a work for Malaysia Dengue Outbreak Detection

Table 3. Comprehensive view of machine learning techniques for liver disease diagnosis.

Machine Learning Techniques	Author	Year	Disease	Resource of Data Set	Tool	Accuracy
SVM	Vijayarani and Dhayanand	2015	Liver Disease	ILPD from UCI	MATLAB	79.66%
Naive Bayes						61.28%
J48						70.669%
MLP						70.8405%
Random Forest	Gulia et al	2014	Liver Disease	UCI	WEKA	71.8696%
SVM						71.3551%
Bayesian Network						69.1252%
Naive Bayes	Rajeswari and Reena	2010	Liver Disease	UCI	WEKA	96.52%
K Star						83.47%
FT tree						97.10%

Figure 5. Accuracy of machine learning algorithms to detect liver disease.

Several studies have investigated the use of data mining models to predict dengue fever, a significant health concern in humid climates like those in Thailand, Indonesia, and Malaysia:

Study on Dengue Prediction using DT, ANN, and RS: This research utilized decision tree (DT), artificial neural network (ANN), and rough set theory (RS) algorithms to predict dengue disease. The dataset was sourced from the Public Health Department of Selangor State. Using the WEKA data mining tool, they conducted two tests: 10-fold cross-validation and percentage split. The 10-fold cross-validation results showed DT with 99.95% accuracy, ANN with 99.98%, and RS with 100%. Using the percentage split, both DT and ANN achieved 99.92% accuracy, while RS scored 99.72%.

Fathima and Manimeglai's Study on Arbovirus-Dengue: They focused on predicting Arbovirus-Dengue using the Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm. The dataset, which included 29 attributes and 5000 samples, was obtained from the King Institute of Preventive Medicine and various hospitals and laboratories in Chennai and Tirunelveli, India. Analysis was conducted using the R project version 2.12.2, with SVM achieving an accuracy of 90.42%.

Ibrahim et al.'s Dengue Fever Forecasting System: This study proposed a system using an artificial neural network for predicting the defervescence day of dengue fever. The data, comprising clinical signs and symptoms, were collected from 252 hospitalized patients, including 4 with Dengue fever (DF) and 248 with dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF). The research utilized MATLAB's neural network toolbox and a multilayer feed-forward neural network (MFNN) algorithm. The MFNN successfully predicted the day of fever subsidence in DF and DHF cases with 90% accuracy.

These studies demonstrate the effectiveness of various data mining and machine learning techniques in diagnosing and predicting dengue fever, highlighting the potential of these technologies in enhancing public health responses to infectious diseases.

Analysis:

Different Machine learning techniques are used to diagnose dengue disease. Dengue disease is one of the serious contagious diseases. As in Table 4, for detection of dengue disease, RS theory shows the highest result as compared to the other algorithms. In 2005 and 2012, researchers used different algorithms but did not attain highest result and improvements. In 2013, accuracy is improved by using RS. It is capable to manage uncertainty, noise and missing data. For the purpose of classification, Developed RS classifier is based on the Rough set theory. Selection of attribute empowers the classifier to surpass the other models. RS is a promising rule based method that offers meaningful information. RS is also best from neural network in term of time. NN takes much time to build model. DT is complex as well as costly algorithm. RS does not need any initial and additional information about data but Decision tree needs information.

Advantages and Disadvantages of RS:

Advantages: It is very easy to understand and provides direct understanding of attained result. It evaluates data significance. It is appropriate for both qualitative and quantitative data. It discovers the hidden patterns. It also finds minimal set of data. It can find relationship that cannot be identified by statistical methods.

Disadvantages: It has not so many limitations still it is not widely used.

Figure 6. Accuracy of machine learning algorithms for dengue disease.

4. Conclusion

The field of assessment has seen an influx of statistical models that often fall short in terms of performance, particularly when dealing with categorical data, missing values, and large datasets. This has underscored the significance of machine learning techniques (MLT), which play a crucial role across various applications including image detection, data mining, natural language processing, and disease diagnostics. MLT have emerged as key solutions in these areas.

This survey paper reviews various machine learning techniques used in the diagnosis of diseases such as heart disease, diabetes, liver disease, dengue, and hepatitis. It's observed that different algorithms excel in identifying attributes accurately, leading to notable results in disease detection. For instance, Support Vector Machine (SVM) has shown to significantly enhance accuracy in heart disease detection with a rate of 94.60%. Naive Bayes stands out in diagnosing diabetes, offering a top classification accuracy of 95%. In liver disease diagnosis, the FT algorithm achieves 97.10% accuracy. Remarkably, Rough Set (RS) theory reaches 100% accuracy in dengue disease detection, while the feed-forward neural network classifies hepatitis with 98% accuracy.

The survey highlights both the advantages and limitations of these algorithms and presents detailed improvement graphs for machine learning algorithms in disease prediction. The analysis clearly demonstrates the enhanced accuracy these algorithms provide across different diseases. Additionally, the paper discusses various tools developed within the AI community, which are instrumental for problem analysis and support improved decision-making processes.

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